

Model of dark matter and dark energy

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Fig.1 Logical map

Abstract

This is a model about dark matter and dark energy.

Introduction

Four factors inspired me. They are: the potential energy curve of quark, the potential energy curve of dark halo, the first law of thermodynamics and the second law of thermodynamics. In the process of building the model, we also found some interesting things. First, the logical map of the model. Figure 1

Part 1 Dark Matter

In this part, the dark matter model is established from the potential energy curve.

We know that the potential energy curve of quarks is like this. Figure 2

Moreover, the potential energy curves of nucleons, atoms and molecules are the same. Let's look at the potential energy curve of the dark halo. Figure 3

Fig. 3 Dark halo Potential energy

Complete and flip the potential energy curve of the dark halo. Figure 4

FIG.4 The complete dark halo potential energy curve

Obviously, part of Figure 2 is very similar to figure 4. The difference is that there is no repulsion in Figure 4. All these potential energy curves have high similarity. Therefore, it can be assumed that they have some similar pattern. For example: dark halo, molecular halo, atomic halo, nucleon halo, quark halo. Put these halos together and they form a concentric sphere. Figure 5

FIG.5 Concentric sphere

According to the principle of field superposition, we believe that the basic composition of the universe is a spherical structure. This sphere has the highest core

density. The density decreases rapidly with the increase of radius, and the radius of the sphere is infinite. We call the sphere **T-unit**. Figure 6

Fig. 6 T-unit

Further, let's look at the gravitational action between two T-units. Obviously, the two spheres do not completely overlap.

We get the definition of **gravity**:

From the point of view of density distribution, gravity is caused by the trend of diffusion from high density to low density. We believe that gravity is a potential energy effect. Moreover, **gravity is positively correlated with density**.

In this way, we get the definition of dark matter:

Dark matter is the low-density part of T-unit. Ordinary matter is the high-density part of T-unit.

Part 2 Dark Energy

In this part, we start with the first law of thermodynamics and the second law of thermodynamics to establish the dark energy model.

When we look for dark energy, we are essentially looking for such a substance: Its number continues to increase, and it expresses repulsion.

The first law of thermodynamics tells us that energy is conserved, and the second law of thermodynamics tells us that the available energy is decreasing. So we come to the conclusion that the unavailable energy is increasing. In other words, low-density materials are increasing. In this way, we found an increasing number of substances. Then let's consider repulsion.

According to the potential energy curve in the part 1, we know that **repulsion** exists in all matter. At the same time, matter has gravity. That is, matter has both repulsion and gravity. Matter is in a **superposition field**. As we all know, matter expresses

repulsion when its density is very high, that is, the **Big Bang**. It is consistent with our daily life experience to express gravity when the density is lower. Finally, when the density is extremely low, does matter express repulsion or gravity? We just said that gravity is positively correlated with density. When the density is very small, the gravity is very small. Then there is a possibility that matter exhibits repulsion at extremely low density. This is consistent with astronomical observations. Dark energy occurs where the density is extremely low. So, we get the curves of gravitational field and repulsive field of matter, Figure 7

Fig. 7 Superposition field

The structure of the superposition field is like a sandwich sugar. Figure 8

Fig. 8 Sandwich sugar

- expresses gravity
- expresses repulsion

Matter of different density has different gravitational regions. The size of the gravitational region is positively correlated with the density of matter.

Thus, we get the definition of dark energy:

Dark energy is the repulsive effect of matter at very high and very low density.

In addition, the second law of thermodynamics also tells us that all interactions cause the overall density of the system to decrease. **That is, all interactions have minimum density requirements.** This is why dark matter hardly interacts with ordinary matter. The density of dark matter is too low to interact with ordinary matter except gravity.

Part 3 Discussion

1. Strong force is the embodiment of gravity at high density.
2. Gravity is only weak on a specific scale.
3. Casimir effect is gravitational effect.
4. etc